

Green Lane Butterfly Surveys

To help us better understand the diversity and abundance of butterflies in the cluster we need your help. This is also a great way to build your skills in butterfly and plant identification. If you would like to get involved, please send us details of the area where you go walking within the Cluster and would like to help us survey the green lanes. We will then send you a map with the lanes marked and you can get started. Whether you can survey one or lots, it all counts.

Methodology

Choose a warm and still day as more butterflies will be on the wing. 10am – 4pm is the best time.

Take a copy of the survey form attached to record your results.

Note the date, time (start and end) and weather.

Mark the map or take a W3W point for the start of your survey. Remember to do this again at the end. This is because it is OK to only survey part of a lane, we just need to calculate the distance surveyed when analysing the results.

Walk along the green lane and record every butterfly that you see, noting the plant (if you can identify it) that it is feeding from. If there are more than one of the same butterfly species together then make a note of the number as well. There may be too many of some species to count e.g., meadow brown, so make an estimate. Some butterflies may be visiting lots of plants, or just flying around the grasses, so note down what you observe or leave blank.

Stop along your walk and complete a timed FIT count. Repeat this as many times as you wish.

If you are able to identify anything else while you are walking up the lane, then we would love to hear about those species too. If possible, with a W3W to record its location.

Send your records to Cath at Launceston farm for collation.

Lastly, have fun!

